

**INFORMED, FREE AND DISCLOSED CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH
In accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki ¹ and the Ovideo Convention ²**

Please read the following information carefully. If you think something is incorrect or unclear, please do not hesitate to ask for more information. If you agree with the proposal made to you, please sign this document.

Study title: Critical Analysis and Evaluation of the User Experience in the Mobile Version of ZeroZero

Background: This research is part of the Master's Dissertation by student Marta Pinhal, entitled “*Critical Analysis and Evaluation of the User Experience in the Mobile Version: Case Study at ZeroZero*”. This research is being carried out as part of the Master's Degree in Information Science at the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, under the supervision of Professor Alexandre Valle de Carvalho.

Explanation of the study: The aim of this study is to understand and evaluate the user experience on the mobile version of ZeroZero, focusing on usability, design and overall satisfaction. To this end, structured interviews will be carried out with users of the platform, in order to explore perceptions, expectations, difficulties and suggestions for improvement related to navigating and using the site on mobile devices.

Participation in the study consists of a **structured interview**, lasting approximately **40 minutes**, which will take place via Zoom. During the interview, participants will be invited to share their experiences with the site, based on a structured set of questions, in an informal setting led by the moderator.

The session will be recorded exclusively for the purposes of academic analysis, and the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants will be guaranteed. The data collected will be used exclusively for academic research purposes, namely for the preparation of the Master's Dissertation and, possibly, for the publication of scientific articles. Participants may, if they wish, have access to the final results of the study.

Conditions and financing: This study is not funded by any institution and participation is entirely voluntary. There are no costs, financial compensation or material benefits associated with your participation. Your decision to participate or not to participate will have no impact on your relationship with the researchers or with ZeroZero.

Confidentiality and anonymity: This study ensures that all data collected will be treated strictly confidentially and used exclusively for the purposes defined in the research. No information will be recorded that allows the personal identification of participants, guaranteeing total anonymity. In addition, all contacts related to the study will be made exclusively in the academic sphere.

I, Marta Garranas Do Novo Pinhal, student on the Master's Degree in Information Science at the University of Porto, with the e-mail address “up202009437@up.pt”, would like to thank (mention the name of the participant) for their availability and willingness to participate in this master's study.

Signature:

I declare that I have read and understood this document, as well as the information provided to me by the person signing above. I have been given the opportunity to refuse to take part in this study at any time without any consequences. I therefore agree to take part in this study and allow the data I provide to be used voluntarily, trusting that it will only be used for this research and the guarantees of confidentiality and anonymity given to me by the researcher.

Name:

Signature:

Date: /..... /.....

**THIS DOCUMENT CONSIST OF 1 PAGE AND IS MADE IN DUPLICATE:
ONE FOR THE RESEARCHER, ONE FOR THE CONSENTING PERSON.**

¹ <http://epidemiologia.med.up.pt/pdfs/Helsing.2013.pdf>

² <http://dre.pt/pdf1sdip/2001/01/002A00/00140036.pdf>